

A new reagent system for the determination of formic acid

Omi Agrawal and V. K. Gupta *

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010, India

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A spectrophotometric method using phloroglucinol is described for the determination of formic acid at ppm level. The method involves the reduction of formic acid by hydrochloric acid and magnesium powder. The formaldehyde so formed is treated with phloroglucinol to give an orange-red coloured dye with λ_{\max} at 475 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 2–15 μg of formic acid per 25 ml of the final solution. The molar absorptivity of the colour system is $6.1 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The method has been applied to the determination of formic acid in biological samples.

Formic acid is a corrosive and highly toxic chemical having considerable significance in forensic science. It is formed in the body due to direct oxidation of denatured alcohol containing methanol and some toxic drug¹. In India many of deaths and physical disorder occur due to inhalation or ingestion of methanol added for denaturing alcohol². Formic acid is widely used as food preservatives. It is commonly used in the production of formyl esters, as a reducing agent in wool, leather, rubber industries and electroplating, as tanning agent and as solvent³.

Here a method is proposed based on the conversion of formic acid to formaldehyde using magnesium powder in hydrochloric acid medium which is subsequently reacted with phloroglucinol to form orange-red coloured dye showing maximum absorbance at 475 nm.

Results and Discussion

The orange-red dye showed λ_{\max} at 475 nm. As the reagent blank has negligible absorbance at this wavelength, all the measurements were made against deionised water. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 2.0–15.0 μg of formic acid in 25 ml of final solution (0.08–0.6 ppm). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $6.1 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0007 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

For reduction, 0.5 ml of 2 M HCl and a pinch of magnesium powder were found to be sufficient to reduce formic acid to formaldehyde. Excess of magnesium powder led to the formation of turbid solution. Reduction of formic acid to formaldehyde was complete in 5 min. Reduction of formic acid at 0° gave the desired result. Constant and maximum absorbance value was obtained when 0.05 M phloroglucinol and 1.5 M sodium hydroxide were taken in the ratio of 3 : 1. Constant absorbance values were found in the pH range 9–10.

The effect of foreign species was studied by addition of various interferants to 10 μg of formic acid before reduc-

tion to formaldehyde. The tolerance limit values (in ppm) are as follows : phenol, benzene, aniline (2800); nitrophenol, trichloroacetic acid, ether (2300); pyridine, isoamyl alcohol (1900); ammonia, K^I, Na^I, Ca^{II}, Fe^{III} (1200); Cl⁻, Br⁻, SO₄²⁻, Zn^{II} (1000); CH₃COO⁻, HCO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, As^{III}, Pb^{II} (900); Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} (50). Other aliphatic acids like propanoic, butanoic, oxalic and succinic did not interfere. Other compounds which are reduced or oxidized to formaldehyde under the proposed condition interfered. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.011 and 2.11% respectively, for seven replicate analysis and statistical error.

Application : As the blood and urine samples analysed did not contain formic acid, synthetic samples were prepared. Blood (serum) and urine samples (~1 ml) were spiked with known amount of formic acid and kept aside for 2 h. The aliquots were analysed by the above procedure. The recoveries were found to be in the range of 95.2–99%.

The proposed method is simple, sensitive, fast, selective and free from the interference of various copollutant. The method can be applied for the analysis of formic acid in biological samples.

Experimental

A Systronics 108 spectrophotometer with matched silica cells and a Systronics 331 pH meter were used.

All reagents were of AnalaR grade. Deionised double-distilled water was used throughout. A stock solution of formic acid (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared and working standard was prepared by appropriate dilution. A mixture of phloroglucinol (Loba Chemie; 0.05 M aqueous) and NaOH (1.5 M aqueous) in the ratio of 3 : 1, was used as absorbing solution. A pinch of magnesium powder in presence of 2 M HCl (0.5 ml) was used as a reducing agent.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing 2.0–15.0 μg of

Note

formic acid, taken in an impinger a pinch of magnesium powder and 2 M HCl (0.5 ml) were added and kept in ice-bath for 10 min and connected to two more impingers each containing 4 ml of absorbing solution, connected to an air sampling train sucking air at a flow rate of $1.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The colourless absorbing solution became orange-red after 15 min. The air was passed for another 35 min. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and the volume made up to 25 ml with water. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 475 nm.

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